

Title: Credit Card Fraud Detection using Big Data

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INTRODUCTION:

Banking and financial industries are facing severe challenges in the form of fraudulent transactions. Credit card fraud is one example of them. In order to detect credit card fraud, we employed Apache Spark a Big Data framework to create a robust credit card fraud detection algorithm.

AIM:

The objectives of credit card fraud detection are to reduce losses due to payment fraud for both merchants and issuing banks and increase revenue opportunities for merchants.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Apache Spark has proved itself to be the next generation BigData processing tool , which has become a favourite for DataScientists and Data Engineers. Its Machine learning component provides well tested scalable algorithms. We will walk through how we used Sparks scalable KMeans algorithm to detect Anomalies for credit card. It will demonstrate a taste of Scala(Sparks Native language) , RDD ,and usage of K-means clustering . And how to improve clustering in a session with Spark.

RESULTS:

Customer behavior is analyzed by spending behavior i.e. categorized into three broad categories: Low Spending Profile, Medium Spending Profile & High Spending Profile. Generally bank customer do not purchase product beyond their income. The customer of a bank generally purchases items of some share of their income. They do not spend the whole income to perform the transaction. The fraud can be identified by using K Mean Clustering algorithm.

CONCLUSIONS:

The purpose is to propose a financial cybercrime detection model that can detect online fraud and to describe various techniques to detect Financial Fraud Detection based on machine learning such as neural network, clustering algorithm. The KMEAN Clustering algorithm is implemented to identify fraudulent transactions based on the spending behavior of a customer. The geographical location of a customer is identified by identifying its IP address and compares the current geographical location with the previous location and identify whether the user can cover entire distance in that time period. If transaction is found to be fraudulent then security system will activate

KEYWORDS:

Credit card fraud; Big Data; Apache Spark; KMEAN;

BIOGRAPHY:

Imane Lasri has completed his Bachelor's degree in Mathematics and Computer Science at the age of 20 years from University Mohammed 5 and now she is a master's student in Big Data engineering at the faculty of science in Mohammed V University Rabat MOROCCO. She have more than 9 certificate from IBM:

Big Data Developer - Mastery Award for Students 2017

Cloud Application Developer - Mastery Award for Students 2016

Big Data Foundations

Hadoop Foundations

Spark

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